

Message from JOQCS Founding Editor-in-Chief

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Dear Reader,

Welcome to the first issue of the Journal of Queer Choral Studies: The Official Academic Publication of GALA Choruses. I am very glad you are here.

I completed my Ph.D. in Music Education at Case Western Reserve University in Cleveland, Ohio, in the spring of 2025. My research was inspired by members of Windsong, Cleveland's Feminist Chorus, the GALA ensemble I have had the privilege of conducting for the past four years. Through conversations with Windsong members, I came to realize that I had a limited understanding of the unique stressors and triumphs experienced by queer older adults, as well as the vital role Windsong played in their lives. During the dissertation process, I found a community of researchers dedicated to preserving, expanding, and demystifying the experiences of queer choral singers and music scholars. There did not, however, appear to be an academic home dedicated primarily to this work.

This journal is unique in many ways. The JOQCS Editorial Board was adamant about making the journal as accessible as possible to readers and researchers alike. JOQCS is an open-access journal; we sought to avoid creating financial barriers to this important research. Additionally, we are excited to welcome a wide variety of perspectives—including researchers, conductors, choir members, and others—as contributors. It is time to bridge the gap between GALA Choruses and the growing field of queer choral research. It feels especially pertinent at this time to elevate queer stories, queer art, queer education, and queer joy.

While assembling this first issue, we encountered setbacks, miscommunications, and frequent revisions of our expectations. One board member jokingly remarked that we were “sight-reading as we were learning the music.” We found that, while we aimed to accept a wide range of articles, clearer parameters were necessary. In future issues, submissions will fall into one of three categories: original research, practitioner articles, and spotlight articles. Interested authors will select the category that best fits their work based on the descriptions in our [Submission Guidelines](#). Authors will also determine whether they would like to participate in a double-anonymous peer review, an open peer review, or an open writing mentorship.

Throughout every step of this journey, I am grateful to GALA Choruses for their support, as well as to our board members and peer reviewers who helped make JOQCS a reality. I am truly excited to see how queer choral research may flourish with the creation of this accessible resource.

Proudly sing on,
Jessica L. Gallagher-Steuver
Founding Editor-in-Chief, The Journal of Queer Choral Studies